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DIFFERENT MATERNAL FACTORS INFLUENCE ON THE BABIES WEIGHT AT TERTIARY CARE HOSPITAL IN WARANGAL, A.P., INDIA

Muppa Leena^{1*}, B. Balaram Nayak²

¹Department of Pharmacy Practice, CL Baid Metha College of Pharmacy, Thoraipakkam, Chennai, India.

²Department of Pediatrics, MGM Hospital, Warangal, A.P, India

Email: jagleena_76@yahoo.com

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Abstract

Background: Low birth weight is the key determinant of infant survival, health and development. LBW is now the leading cause of death globally for children five. The health of a pregnant woman has a profound effect on the health of the fetus and new born. This study was carried out to find out the impact of different maternal factors on the birth weight of newborns.

Aim and objectives: To find out different maternal factors influence on the babies weight and to study which one of the various factors had maximum influence on low birth weight.

Method: Total 120 patients were recruited for the study, consisted of 60 LBW as cases and NBW as controls. A personal interview was carried out with the pre-designed questionnaire information regarding the maternal factors like maternal age, parity, spacing between pregnancies, maternal education, mother occupation was noted. The results were analyzed and computed.

Results: Among study population the average weight of the low birth weight babies was 1.624 ± 0.41 (in grams). The mean age among the mothers of neonates was found to be 21.95 ± 4.47 . Maternal age <than 19 years, had high proportions of low birth weight babies (50%). Laborers' occupation had a negative effect on the birth weight as compared to housewives and service class women. The birth interval and bad obstetric history of mother were significantly associated with birth weight of the new born.

Conclusion: Maternal gestational age at the time of delivery was the only single parameter had significant negative impact on birth weight. Maternal occupation, maternal education, previous bad obstetric histories were

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also found to be a major risk factor responsible for LBW. Improving female literacy, optimizing the age of pregnancy, adoption of temporary family planning practices for regulating fertility might improve the birth weight of new born babies.

Key words: Maternal factors, low birth weight, Pre-term, Mother gestational age.

Introduction

Birth weight is the first weight of the fetus or new born obtained after birth, preferably measured within the first hour of life before significant postnatal weight loss has occurred. Birth weight is a major determinant of child's health and nutrition [1]. Low birth weight (LBW) by international agreement has been defined as a birth weight of less than 2500 grams (WHO1976). Annually there are almost 23 million LBW infants worldwide per 121 million births, a high proportion of which are in developing countries [2]. The health of a pregnant woman has a profound effect on the health of the foetus and new born. In India, birth weight has remained low and the prevalence of LBW is about 33% as compared to 4.5% in industrially developed countries [3].

As evidenced by the fact that LBW babies are 40 times greater contributors to neonatal mortality and morbidity [4]. Even if an LBW baby survives, it likely to suffer a high incidence of malnutrition, diarrhea, acute respiratory infection, infectious disease, neurodevelopment problems such as cerebral palsy, and physical defects. In addition, LBW also determines the postnatal mental, physical, and neurological development of children [5].

The study was aimed to find out the effect of various maternal risk factors on the birth weight with the objectives: (1) to study the effect of various factors associated with outcome of LBW and (2) to study which one of the various factors had maximum impact on LBW. In addition the purpose of the study is to increase education and awareness regarding low birth weight and its complication.

Materials and Methods

The case-control study was conducted at the in-patient department of Pediatrics and in NICU department of Mahatma Gandhi Memorial Hospital, Warangal, which is a 1200 bedded multidisciplinary government & tertiary care hospital. The study was carried out for the period of one year i.e. between the months of January 2018 to September 2018. Total of 120 neonates were included in the study as per inclusion and exclusion

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criteria, consisted of 60 Low birth weight (LBW) as cases and 60 normal birth weight (NBW) as controls.

Informed consent was obtained from each mother of participant neonates recruited for the study.

A personal interview was carried out with the predesigned questionnaire. Information regarding the maternal factors (independent variables) like maternal age, parity, spacing between pregnancies, Pregnancy induced hypertension, mother education, mother occupation, and birth history like place of delivery, gestational age at delivery was also obtained. The results were analyzed and computed.

The descriptive analysis was performed calculating the distribution of cases and controls within categories of maternal factors. The reference group within separate age and maternal factors was that with the lowest proportion of LBW, i.e. 20–25 years old mothers, house wives, gestational age ≥ 37 weeks, living in urban area. X^2 statistics were calculated initially to describe the relationship between all independent variables and LBW (dependent variable). Two tailed probability (p) values of less than 0.05 were considered to indicate statistical significance. Odds ratios (OR) to deliver LBW baby according to maternal factors and their corresponding 95% confidence intervals (CI) were calculated by using graph pad prism version 5.

Results and Discussion

Number of researchers stated that maternal socio-economic factors (education, income and employment status) are associated with particular health behavior peculiarities and health status that can further directly influence the newborn's health.

The present thesis work was carried out to assess the birth weight pattern in study group and to identify and assess the impact of certain vulnerable factors influencing the birth weight.

Among the study population the mean weight (in grams) of low birth weight babies was 1.624 ± 0.14 (mean \pm SD) and normal birth weight babies was 2.83 ± 0.25 . In the study 67 (57.8%) were male babies. Out of 120 deliveries 39% were caesarean delivery.

In the present study, the proportion of low birth weight (LBW) was highest among maternal age group ranged 14-19 (OR 6.9) as compared to age groups 20-25 and > 25 years. Similar findings confirmed by study conducted by Mukherji D.K et al (1970) [6], Fedric J et al (1976) [7], and Anand K et al (2000) [8]. Mothers

less than 19 years old are prone to have physical and emotional maturity issues which may contribute to the elevated number of LBW infants.

Some investigation concluded that maternal education remains a significant factor increasing the risk to deliver LBW baby. In this study we have observed that, among study population 33(55%) neonates were born to illiterate mothers. Which is similar to the study, conducted by S.S Hirve et al [9], found that the risk of LBW is directly correlated with mother's education and accounted for 41.4 % of LBW cases. Low educational status leads to low health conscious and low ante natal attendance leading to the increased risk of LBW babies.

Results from various study showed the association between maternal occupation during pregnancy and infant's birth weight. According to the literature review, women who were employed during pregnancy had the higher risk of low birth weight as compared with unemployed.

Study conducted by Jolanka Dickute et al (2004) [10], found that, maternal occupation was associated with the highest risk to deliver LBW baby. In the present study out of 48 laborer mothers 37 (77.1 %) laborer mothers delivered LBW babies. The odds ratio for occupation shows that as compared to house wives, mothers who were involved in the service had much lower risk (OR 1.07) of having LBW where as laborer (OR 3.71) had higher risk of having LBW babies. This clearly shows that, it is not the working status of mother which affect birth weight but type of maternal occupation. Similar findings were observed by Shah U.P et al (2013) [11].

In the present study, gestational age at delivery was found to be significantly related with low birth weight of babies ($p < 0.0001$). Comparison of LBW babies was done with gestational age at delivery, pre-term deliveries (<37 weeks) accounted for 48 (92 %) as compare to 12 (17.6 %) for full term deliveries. This is similar to the study conducted by Lt Col G Singh et al (2009) [12]. Impact of preterm delivery was found to be the highest risk factor with odds ratio 66.7, (95% CI 18.40-200.1) as compared to all other maternal factors.

It was observed that percentage of low birth weight increased with an increase in parity (57.6%-1st order, 72.4-2nd order, 80%- 3rd order). Similar findings are confirmed by the study carried out by Iceberg et al (1992) [13].

Spacing between 2 consecutive pregnancies had a highly significant influence on the percentage of low birth weight i.e. more the spacing between 2 consecutive pregnancy les the incidence of low birth weight babies.

Muppa Leena*et al. /International Journal of Pharmacy & Technology (66.6%-< 2, 57.1 %->4). Similar findings confirmed by study conducted by Gawde et al [14] and Desmukh et al. (1998) [15].

The study data shows that pregnancy induced hypertension was a significant contributing factor towards LBW babies (80%, (P=0.006). Study conducted by Lt Col G Singh et al (2009)¹², were also observed the same findings.

In the present study, previous Bad obstetric history (BOH) was significantly related with LBW babies i.e. 83.3 % (5 out of 6 mothers) of the women with BOH in the past gave birth to LBW newborns in the present pregnancy. This in compliance with the study conducted, by Silvia de Sanjose et al (1991) [16]. Hence this study says that, BOH should also to be considering as a major deciding factor on low birth weight neonates.

Results are given in Table No.1

Table1: Relationship of different maternal factors with birth weight.

Maternal Factors	LBW	NBW	P- Value	OR	Confidence Interval (95%)	
	N=60 (%)	N=60 (%)			Upper	lower
Maternal Age (years)						
14-19	30 (50)	16 (26.7)	0.0012	4.081	1.769	9.412
20-25	13 (21.6)	37 (61.7)	ref	1		
>25	17 (28.3)	7 (11.66)	0.0154	0.2474	0.0837	0.7313
Maternal Education						
Literate	27 (45)	48 (80)	0.006	3.273	1.453	7.371
Illiterate	33 (55)	12(20)				
Maternal Occupation						
Housewife	14 (23.3)	35 (58.3)	ref	1		
Labour	37 (61.7)	11(18.33)	0.034	3.71	1.548	8.705

Service	09 (15)	14 (23.33)	1.00(N.S)	1.071	0.3733	3.075
Maternal Residence						
Rural	54 (90)	43 (71.7)	ref	1		
Urban	06 (10)	17 (28.3)	0.019	0.281	0.102	0.7743
Gestational age at delivery						
≥37 weeks	12 (20)	56 (93.3)	ref	1		
≤ 37 weeks	48 (80)	4 (6.7)	0.006	6.67	1.84	20.01
Gravida of Mother						
1st	19 (31.7)	14 (23.3)	0.0049	4.071	1.573	10.54
2 nd	12 (20)	36 (60)	ref	1		
>2	29 (48.3)	10 (16.7)	0.0001	0.1149	0.04351	0.3037
PIH of Mother						
Yes	16 (26.7)	4 (6.7)	0.006	0.1964	0.0612	0.629
No	44 (73.3)	56 (93.3)				

Conclusion

The study showed that, as a single parameter maternal gestational age had the highest adverse impact on the birth weight of a baby. The analysis of relations between LBW and different maternal factors showed that, highest rates of LBW were found among young maternal age i.e. < 19 years, at the time of delivery. Maternal occupation i.e. laborer mothers and previous BOH were also found to be a major risk factor responsible for LBW babies. This study indicate that improving female literacy, optimizing the age of pregnancy and avoiding close birth interval are essential measures for reducing prevalence of LBW babies.

The study also recommends undertaking of a similar type of study in the same population on a wider scale, to confirm the findings of the above study. Creating awareness on the factors identified in the present study is very important, to reduce the overall incidence of low birth weight and its complications in the community.

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Corresponding Author:

Muppa Leena Mpharm.,

Assistant Professor, CL Baid Metha College of Pharmacy, Thoraipakkam, Chennai.

Email: jagleena_76@yahoo.com